

Falcon

Foreseeing **the next generation** of Aircraft

D5.1 Report on selection of development platforms and computational resources

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List of acronyms

EU	European Union
FSI	Fluid-Structure Interaction
FEM	Finite Element Model
LBM	Lattice Boltzmann Methods
WP	Work Package
NH	Node Hours

BACKGROUND: ABOUT THE FALCON PROJECT

The FALCON project is a Research and Innovation Action funded by the Horizon Europe – the Framework Programme for Research and Innovation (2021-2027) aiming to develop a hybrid approach combining both cutting-edge numerical and experimental methods to analyze Fluid-Structure Interaction (FSI), better predict and control the aircraft aerodynamic unsteady loads, thus improving the aeroelastic properties and sustainability of aerostructures and reducing the related aerodynamical noise. This will ultimately contribute to upscale the current design capabilities of the European aircraft industry while enhancing the digital transformation of the European supply chain.

The project is implemented by a European consortium with 8 world-class partners including: i) Internationally recognized research groups in fluid-structure interaction using numerical simulation (AMU, KIT) and experiments (DLR); ii) Major companies developing numerical simulation software for fluid dynamics (CS) and solid dynamics. (MSC); iii) An internationally renowned research center for high-performance computing (IT4I@VSB); a leading company in France for the funding obtention, communication and dissemination of EU projects (EURONOVIA) and iv) a major actor in the European aeronautical industry (AIRBUS).

To upscale the actual design capabilities of the aeronautics industry, FALCON addresses open key-problems involving FSI phenomena to reduce noise and improve sustainability, based on a conceptual methodology built on four pillars: MEASURE, SIMULATE, BOOST, OPTIMIZE.

Figure 1: FALCON conceptual approach

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document is a deliverable of the FALCON Project, funded under the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under the grant agreement No 101138305.

The goal of this deliverable is to report the status of the access to the HPC systems that will be used for code development and optimization, benchmarking, and running FSI simulations by members of the consortium.

The key development system Karolina at IT4I was identified. It is accessible through the Multiyear project for all project partners. This system contains both CPU and GPU partitions that allow development of both MSC+LaBS and ESPRESO+OpenLB FSI simulations. In addition, Karolina also hosts the hybrid database with experimental data and simulation results.

Besides Karolina, the code is developed on HoreKa at KIT and AMU Mesocentre. Consortium also use pre-exascale clusters LUMI at CSC and Leonardo at CINECA. The pre-exascale systems will be used for running large scale FSI simulations and training surrogate models.

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1. Introduction

This deliverable describes development platforms and computation resources that will be used by FALCON members during this project. It provides basic hardware information about used systems, submitted and planned proposals, and account creation and environment settings for the main development platforms.

2. Identification of development platforms

IT4I leads securing computational resources to European system that are necessary to develop and optimize, benchmark, and run FSI simulations with all partners of the project. Based on proposal and discussion with partners, the following systems have been identified.

2.1. IT4I Karolina

partition	#nodes	CPU	accelerator	memory	Theoretical peak perf.
w/o accelerator	720	2 × AMD EPYC 7H12; 2.6 GHz, 64 cores	-	256 GB	3.8 PFlop/s
accelerated	70	2 × AMD EPYC 7763; 2.45 GHz, 64 cores	8 × Nvidia A100	1024 GB	11.6 PFlop/s
data analytics	1	32 × Intel Xeon Platinum; 2.9 GHz, 24 cores	-	24 TB	71.3 TFlop/s
Cloud	36	2 × AMD EPYC 7H12; 2.6GHz, 64 core	-	256 GB	192 TFlop/s

Karolina is the largest system that operates IT4I with 720 universal and 70 accelerated nodes. It is the key developing platform allowing to run both MSC Nastran+LaBS and ESPRESO+OpenLB coupled simulations. For MSC Nastran+LaBS CPU partition will be used, ESPRESO+OpenLB use accelerated partition with NVidia A100 accelerators.

Karolina also hosts a hybrid database with experimental and numerical data.

2.2. LUMI

partition	#nodes	CPU	accelerator	memory	Linpack perf.
w/o accelerator	2048	2 × AMD EPYC 7763; 2.45 GHz, 64 cores	-	256 GB	7.63 PFlop/s
accelerated	2978	2 × AMD EPYC 7763; 2.45 GHz, 64 cores	4 × AMD MI250x	1024 GB	379.7 PFlop/s

LUMI is a pre-exascale system equipped with AMD MI250x accelerators. These accelerators are not currently suitable for running FSI simulations. Hence, the system will be primarily used for training surrogate models.

2.3. KIT HoreKa

partition	#nodes	CPU	accelerator	memory	Linpack perf.
w/o accelerator	570	2x Intel Xeon Platinum 8368; 2.4 GHz, 38 cores	-	256 GB	3.51 PFlop/s
accelerated	167	2x Intel Xeon Platinum 8368; 2.4 GHz, 38 cores	4 × Nvidia A100 (40 GB HBM each)	512 GB	15.01 PFlop/s
accelerated_h100	22	2x AMD EPYC 9354; 3.25 GHz, 32 cores	4 x Nvidia H100 (95 GB HBM each)	768 GB	5.96 PFlop/s

HoreKa is a hybrid system equipped with more than 60,000 processor cores, close to 300 terabytes of main memory and more than 750 Nvidia A100 and H100 GPUs. It is a Tier-2 national scale system hosted at KIT within the framework of NHR in Germany. OpenLB can utilize both the unaccelerated HoreKa blue partition (MPI+OpenMP, AVX-512) and the accelerated partitions (HoreKa green and teal) via CUDA. It is the primary development target cluster for OpenLB.

2.4. CINECA Leonardo

partition	#nodes	CPU	accelerator	memory	Linpack perf.
w/o accelerator	1536	2 × Intel Sapphire Rapids; 4.8 GHz, 56 cores	-	512 GB	9 PFlop/s
accelerated	3456	1 × Intel Xeon 8358; 2.6 GHz, 32 cores	4 × NVidia A100 SXM6	512 GB	240 PFlop/s

Leonardo is a pre-exascale system equipped with NVidia A100 SXM6 64GB accelerators. The key role of this system will be to provide resources for high-scale FSI simulations with ESPRESO+OpenLB.

2.5. AMU Mesocentre

partition	#nodes	CPU	accelerator	memory	Linpack perf.
w/o accelerator	158	1 × Intel Xeon Gold 6142; 2.6 GHz, 32 cores	-	192 GB	

AMU Mesocentre will be used to perform validation on academic FSI configuration with ProLB.

3. Securing computational resources

This section contains a list of submitted and planned proposals prepared by IT4I and KIT in order to secure the computational resources needed to perform the work described in the FALCON project proposal.

3.1. Submitted proposals

This section contains a list of submitted and already accepted proposals with their basic parameters.

3.1.1. Fast track access for IT4I Karolina

The preliminary access to IT4I Karolina was achieved by the “fast track access” to get access as soon as possible.

- submitted at: 26.1.2024
- purpose: enabling to create IT4I account for all project partners, installation of libraries, initial testing.
- project period: 6 months (12.2.2024 - 13.6.2024)
- number of resources (NH):
 - Karolina GPU: 500; Karolina CPU: 5200

3.1.2. Multi-Year Open Project for IT4I systems

The main project to secure computational resources for code development, optimization, and access and creation of a hybrid database. The project started at M6, and its duration is 3 years. Hence, a similar project will also be submitted before the last year of the FALCON project to secure the remaining 6 months of the FALCON project. The project also contains resources for the LUMI cluster. The number of resources is specified differently for each year. It corresponds to the expected needs of the FALCON consortium members for computation resources.

- submitted: 4.4.2024
- purpose: code development, optimization, build and store hybrid database, benchmarking, run small and middle size simulations.
- project period: 36 months (30.5.2024 - 29.5.2027)
- number of resources, year 1 (NH):
 - Karolina GPU: 300; Karolina CPU: 2,900
 - LUMI GPU: 10,000; LUMI CPU: 700
- number of resources, year 2 (NH):
 - Karolina GPU: 1,200; Karolina CPU: 11,600
 - LUMI GPU: 25,000; LUMI CPU: 10,000
- number of resources, year 3 (NH):
 - Karolina GPU: 6,000; Karolina CPU: 11,600
 - LUMI GPU: 50,000; LUMI CPU: 2,800

3.1.3. Multi-Year Project for KIT systems

KIT utilizes an existing computational project on HoreKa for OpenLB developments in the context of FALCON. The CPE2 computational project focuses on developing a high-performance framework for adjoint-based optimization on GPGPU clusters. The project currently runs to 31 July 2025 and is planned to be extended on an annual basis.

- submitted: May 24
- purpose: code development, performance engineering, adjoint optimization, benchmarking, run of up to medium size simulations
- project period: 12 months (01.07.24-31.07.25)
- number of resources
 - HoreKa blue (CPU): 36.22e6 [core-h]
 - HoreKa green/teal (GPU): 0.48e6 [GPU-h]

3.2. Planned proposals

This section contains a list of planned proposals to secure resources for large-scale simulations. It is planned to submit proposals when FSI simulations will be implemented and optimized.

3.2.1. Regular Access to Leonardo

To secure resources for large-scale FSI simulations, a proposal for regular access to the Leonardo cluster will be submitted. The consortium will prepare this proposal when tools (ESPRESO and OpenLB) fully support coupled FSI simulations and will be prepared for large scale production runs.

A prerequisite for regular access is to have the tools benchmarked on the system. Hence, benchmark and development access will precede the regular access proposal. In this benchmarking period, the number of resources will be denoted. Currently, the number of NHs similar to the LUMI cluster is expected.

4. Set-up of development systems

This section contains a description of the process of creating a user account, setting the environment, and installation of tools on development platforms.

4.1. Creation of user accounts at IT4I

The process of creating a user account for the IT4I systems is described in the documentation available at <https://docs.it4i.cz/general/access/account-introduction/>. When the user account is created, one needs to log into the IT4I SCS portal available at <https://scs.it4i.cz/> to submit a request to become a project member of one of the active projects described in the previous section. Then, it is possible to log into the IT4I systems via SSH as is described at <https://docs.it4i.cz/general/shell-and-data-access/>.

4.2. Creation of user accounts at LUMI

Access to the LUMI cluster is available with the same computational project as for Karolina. A description is available at <https://docs.lumi-supercomputer.eu/firststeps/accessLUMI/>.

4.3. Creation of user accounts at HoreKa

The process to create a new user account on the NHR@KIT system HoreKa is described at <https://www.nhr.kit.edu/userdocs/horeka/registration/>.

4.4. Installation of ESPRESO

ESPRESO is open-source tool publicly available at <https://github.com/It4innovations/espresso>. After cloning the repository on Karolina, it can be installed with the following commands:

```
$ . env/it4i.karolina.openmpi.mkl.32.sh
```

```
$ ./waf configure
```

```
$ ./waf
```

The first script loads modules OpenMPI/4.1.6-GCC-13.2.0, OpenBLAS/0.3.24-GCC-13.2.0, imkl/2024.2.0, CMake/3.27.6-GCCcore-13.2.0, Boost/1.83.0-GCC-13.2.0, Eigen/3.4.0-GCCcore-13.2.0, Python/3.11.5-GCCcore-13.2.0, Boost.Python-NumPy and install third-party libraries METIS, ParMETIS, SuiteSparse, and preCICE.

Installation can be validated by a set of pre-defined tests in the repository, e.g.:

```
$ sh tests/run.basic.sh
```

The repository also contains configuration file for test related to FALCON project at directory 'tests/falcon'.

4.5. Installation of OpenLB

OpenLB is an open-source LBM framework publicly available at <https://openlb.net>. After downloading the current release (or cloning the release repository at <https://gitlab.com/openlb/release>) or cloning the FALCON-internal development repository at <https://gitlab.com/openlb/falcon> on HoreKa, it can be compiled for multi-GPU execution with the following commands:

```
$ module load toolkit/nvidia-hpc-sdk/22.3
```

```
$ cp config/gpu_horeka_nvdiiahpc_mixed.mk config.mk
```

```
$ make
```

```
$ cd $caseDirectory # exchange
```

```
$ make
```

The HoreKa configuration also includes an appropriate SLURM script. The build can be checked using the integrated benchmark and unit test (not currently in public release) suite via:

```
$ make check
```

```
$ make benchmark
```

Building and running jobs on Karolina works analogously, a basic configuration is provided in `config/gpu_karolina_mixed.mk`.

5. Conclusion

Access to the key development system Karolina was secured through a multi-year project. Besides providing computational resources, it will also host a hybrid database with both experimental and numerical data.

Karolina is suitable for the development of FSI simulation by all tools used in the FALCON project (MSC Nastran + LaBS, ESPRESO+OpenLB). It is possible to run small and mid-size tests on this system. The LUMI cluster with many AMD accelerators is available for training surrogate models. Due to a limited number of GPU resources on Karolina, access to the CINECA Leonardo system will be requested when coupled FSI simulation with ESPRESO + OpenLB will be prepared for production runs.